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THREE-DIMENSIONAL SURFACE AREA OF THE ANTERIOR CRUCIATE LIGAMENT TIBIAL INSERTION AND ITS CORRELATION WITH THE ANATOMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PROXIMAL TIBIA

Nemanja Kovačev¹, Zoran Milojević², Milan Milović³, Vukadin Milankov^{4,5}

- 1 HTEC Group, Beograd, Serbia
- 2 Faculty of Technical Sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia
- 3 General Hospital, Vrbas, Serbia
- 4 Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
- 5 Institute for Health Care of Children and Youth of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

Introduction. Precise positioning of the tibial tunnel is crucial for successful anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction, complementing the focus on femoral tunnel placement. By correlating the anterior cruciate ligament attachment area on the tibia with the tibial plateau size on standard radiographs, the drilling angle can be determined using two preoperative radiographs.

Material and Methods. The study analyzed 32 proximal tibial surfaces with anterior cruciate ligament attachments obtained during total knee arthroplasty. Preoperative anteroposterior and lateral radiographs were used to measure tibial plateau dimensions. Three-dimensional scanning of the anterior cruciate ligament attachment area relative to the tibial articular surface was performed using the Personal Haptic Interface Mechanism Omni device. This provided two new measurements: the ACL attachment area (mm²) and its projection on the tibia (mm²).

Results. The average anteroposterior diameter was 47.81mm, while the average medial-lateral diameter was 71.94mm. The average anterior cruciate ligament attachment area was 142.4mm², and the average projection area was 110.2mm². Analysis of variance in multiple regression showed that measuring both diameters could achieve statistically significant correlations. Mathematical-statistical procedures were used to derive formulas for calculating the attachment area and projection based on measured anteroposterior and medial-lateral diameters of the tibial plateau. The surface area can be predicted using the formula $P=7.585 \times AP - 0.179 \times ML - 207.319$. and projection area $P=3.466 \times AP + 1.261 \times ML - 146.218$.

Conclusion. Measuring tibial plateau dimensions on radiographs allows accurate prediction of the attachment area. Combined with drill bit diameter, this enables determination of the tibial tunnel drilling angle.

Contact: Prof. dr sc. med. Vukadin Milankov, Institute for Health Care of Children and Youth of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia,
+381 64 66 1 222 4,
vukadin.milankov@mf.uns.ac.rs